

Sizonenko V., Sinitsyn I. Experience of UNDBE model application on examples radionuclide pollution transport of the Loire River (France) and Kiev reservoir (Ukraine)

Since the late 1960s it was realized that advection dispersion equations (ADE) did not describe observed tracer profiles in many cases. The most important of these is its prediction of Gaussian spatial concentration distributions, whereas observed concentration distributions are invariably skewed with long tails. The aggregated dead zone (ADZ) model is one of the transport models that has been categorized as mechanistic data-driven models and is devoid of these drawbacks. ADZ is less known than ADE models and not used previously for modeling radionuclide pollution transport. Rather than modelling solute concentration continuously in both distance and time along a reach as in the case of the ADE model, the ADZ model takes a “black box” approach and simply considers the reach output concentration as a function of the reach input concentration and time. This greatly reduces the computation time and decreases the requirements on the amount of initial and boundary data. The ADZ model assumes an instantaneous and complete mixing within the aggregated dead zone and steady flow conditions such that the discharge Q and ADZ volume V are constant.

The UNDBE model represents an attempt to extend ADZ for real water bodies with non-conservative radioactive contamination. It is assumed that the object is divided into separate consecutive boxes and time into separate time intervals when there is constancy Q and volume of box (data constancy intervals are common practice in the study of water bodies). The model uses differential equations with a delayed argument T_R . Transportation time T_R - depends on the flow rate and the length of the box. Its dynamics are determined by calibrating the hydrological model of the water object. For solving differential equations with a delayed argument, the RETARD program [1] was used. The proposed model provides for the determination of concentrations in solution, in suspension and in the bottom sediments. When using the proposed model, it will be necessary to determine seven parameters. These parameters are determined by parametric identification from the measurement data. The RALG program (search for the extremum of an undifferentiated multivariate function) was used [2].

UNDBE was used to model the transfer of ^3H in the Loire River channel. There are five nuclear power plants in the Loire River basin, which release ^3H into the water. Hydrologic and ^3H emission data were presented in 1-hour data constancy intervals. It was necessary to determine the dynamics of ^3H concentrations at 11 points along the riverbed with an hourly discreteness, within six months. The 350 km long river section was described by specifying the geometry of 486 cross sections. The river channel was divided into 33 consecutive boxes. A one-dimensional steady-state hydrologic model to determine the current boxes volumes was used. The calculation of the hydrology of the Loire River (for each hour of the six-month modeling interval, for 33 boxes) requires 20 minutes of computer time with an Intel Core i5-9600K processor. Solving the ^3H transport problem takes 8 seconds. Since the hydrological regime of the river does not depend on ^3H transport, the calculation of the water regime was performed once for the entire range of possible water flows, and the results were used as an array of input data for multiple calculations for identifying parameters of ^3H transport. The Fig. 1 a part of the modeling results - the dynamics of ^3H (Bq/l) in the point Angier (line) compared to the measurement data (dots) and a 30% error.

For the Dnipro reservoir cascade (6 reservoirs), are only daily data. Calculations were made for 1991, 1994, and 1999, when there were significant increases in the ^{90}Sr concentration in the Pripjat River (the main source of ^{90}Sr). Kyiv reservoir: length 110 km, volume 2.7 - 3.9 km³ (depending on the level). Since all significant tributaries (including the Pripjat River) are located at the inlet of the reservoir, and the place where it was necessary to determine the concentration values was the water intake point - the city of Vyshhorod (the outflow), the reservoir was modeled with one box. The hydrological and toxicological parameters of the Kyiv reservoir were identified and tentatively (due to the lack of toxicological data) for other reservoirs.

Fig. 1 Concentration of ^3H , Angier (Bq/l)

In Fig. 2 the comparison of calculations (line) and measurements of ^{90}Sr concentrations in the area of Vyshgorod in 1999 (Bq/m^3). Different colored dots represent measurement data from different organizations. Measurement accuracy is from 30 to 50%. Time of calculation one-year interval for 6 reservoirs less 0.1 sec.

Fig. 2 Concentration of ^{90}Sr , Vyshgorod (Bq/m^3)

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